

Reading Note – Relations internationales de l'Iran 2

- INALCO – EUUB420b - Relations internationales de l'Iran 2 – Reading Note
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Article 1 : “*Reclaiming Iraq – The 1920 revolution and the founding of the modern state*”, by Abbas Kadhim (2012), University of Texas Press – Chapter 3 - *The revolution in the middle Euphrates and beyond* – p. 69-96.

Article 2 : “*The 1920 revolt in Iraq reconsidered – The role of tribes in national politics*”, by Amal Vinogradov (1972), *Int. J. Middle East Stud.* 3 – p. 123-139.

1. Authors and Articles

Abbas Kadhim, born in 1965, graduated with a PhD in Near Eastern Studies from the University of California in Berkeley and is an expert on Iraq. Since 2018, he is resident fellow at the Atlantic Council and leads the Iraq Initiative within the Middle East Programs. Previously, he was senior foreign policy fellow at Johns Hopkins University’s School of Advanced International Studies and a visiting assistant professor at Stanford University. He also held a senior government affairs position at the Iraqi Embassy in Washington, DC. He is the author of “*Reclaiming Iraq: The 1920 Revolution and the Founding of the Modern State*”, “*Governance in the Middle East and North Africa*” and “*The Hawza Under Siege: Studies in the Ba’th Party Archive*”.

Amal Rassam Vinogradov is a US based women ethnologist and anthropologist who graduated at Ann Arbor-Michigan University and lectured at Queens College-City University of New York. Her most quoted contributions were the book “*The Ait Ndhir in Morocco : A study of the transformation of a Berber tribe*” (1974) and various articles including the “*The 1920 revolt in Iraq reconsidered – The role of tribes in national politics*” (1972), “*Ethnicity, Cultural Discontinuity and Power Brokers in Northern Iraq: The Case of the Shabak*” (1974), published in the *International Journal of Middle East Studies* and the *American Ethnologist*.

2. Summary of Abbas Kadhim's article

The British did not see the Iraqi revolution coming. On 30th June 1920, the spark was a minor financial debt issue of a local sheikh with the British authorities, ill handled by the local political officer. But a coordinated revolt movement was already underway in the Shia holy cities. The root cause of it was the ever-postponed independence, promised of the British, and the military and administrative heavy-handed repression of those reminding them.

Incidents started with the violent release from prison of the sheikh, the siege of the small British garrison in Rumaitha by local tribes and the destruction of a railway section. The British forces had to deal simultaneously with similar situations throughout the country albeit deteriorated transportation facility and a depleted operational force of only 34.200 soldiers available against a theoretical 133.000. A violent retaliation attack on a village ended up in a severe British defeat and an incentive and additional grievances for further Iraqi revolts. On the 6th of July, a rescue force, heading for the besieged Rumaitha camp, had to retreat with heavy losses. Blind offensives by the British forces led to multiple incidents and civilian casualties, while successful ambushes raised anxieties of commanding officer General Haldane. Finally, on 20th of July, the Rumaitha garrison was pulled back to reinforce the Baghdad southern defence line in Hilla on the Euphrates.

But revolt was soaring too near Najaf among other rival southern tribes. They demanded British forces withdrawal, despite good relationships with more subtle local British officers. These forces retreated and entrenched themselves in Kufa, south of Hilla. Iraqi tribes started advancing on both cities and soon controlled almost the entirety of southern Mesopotamia after the British had evacuated Najaf and Kerbala. On 25th of July, a rescue team sent from Hilla to Kufa was defeated in Raranjiyya and artillery was captured by the insurgents. The equipment was immediately put in use in the Kufa siege to sink a protecting British river gunboat. Unfortunately for the Iraqi insurgents, a three-front attack on Kufa failed because of their lack of synchronism.

The siege on Kufa was lifted and the Iraqi troops joined back the main battle front on Hilla. Meanwhile, the British failed in an offensive on Kerbala, a major centre for the rebellion, leaving to the Iraqis a new stockpile of equipment and ammunitions.

The upheaval lingered in the middle Euphrates. Upstarts in the northern part where both late and limited in time. They sometimes joined in the uprising because of local British abuses but soon backed off as they had no profound feuds against them. Several northern sheikhs even took side with the British and helped quell the rebellion in their area.

By mid-August, the rebellion expanded to the southern Euphrates and found local supportive sheikhs. British political officers managed to secure loyalties based on personal connections or by way of intimidation using airplanes flying low over turbulent cities. But loyalties of notables did not suffice to control looting mobs and the British had to evacuate key cities in the south. Nonetheless, local tribes did not take military advantage of this situation and soon engaged in peace settlement talks with the British.

To the east of Baghdad, in the region of Diyala, railway tracks were wrecked by tribes and a couple of cities were evacuated by the British and left to pillage. By the end of August, all the territories north of Baghdad were lost to British control. But within two months, the two cities were recaptured and a mild, mainly financial, punishment was inflicted to alleged revolt leaders.

The revolt lasted for a few more months, but the tribes had limited action means because of food and ammunition shortages. The British managed to get military reinforcements and above all benefited from their equipment superiority both on the ground and in the air. In October, they took the insurgents' stronghold position on their way to Kerbala, which for fear of destructions surrendered to the British. As a punishment, the provisional rebel government was imprisoned and all rifles and ammunitions were confiscated. Within days, the siege of Kufa was lifted by an attacking British force and consequently, the city of Najaf surrendered to the British under similar conditions as Kerbala. It took until November to subdue the last tribes which finally surrendered to Baghdad under much more favourable conditions, including the promise of a face-saving acceptance of an "Arab independent government", which anyway had already been decided upon in London.

It is unclear if the Abu Tabikh regional rebel government erected in Kerbala really had a wider national mission in prospect. Abu Tabikh is depicted in memoirs of Iraqi contemporaries as a true revolutionary, generous to the cause. His involvement against the British dates back to 1915 when he sided with the Ottomans in the Jihad against the non-Muslim British invaders of Iraq. Abu Tabikh later wrote that the British occupation authority took great care in showing great respect to the notabilities and landowners, which did not extend to ordinary Iraqi folks. Yet this obsequious policy could vary deeply according to individual British political agents' personalities.

On 5th of July 1920, Karbala's notabilities demanded that Iraq should be granted independence, that Iraqi prisoners be released, and that the British forces should regrouped in Baghdad until a final agreement was signed. But their local British agent interlocutor could not commit on such wide terms and the extension of the war nullified these talks. A provisory government was erected in Kerbala. Abu Tabikh, a non-citizen of Karbala, was designated (symbolically on the Shia

commemoration-day of Ali's nomination by the Prophet as his successor) to head the government with a definite national and not regional mandate. A national Iraqi flag was publicly raised on Kerbala city-hall, in front of cheering crowds. There is a "who-raised-the-flag first" controversy because of the latter significance of it in modern Iraq history regarding the first genuine Iraqi national self-proclaimed government. British diplomatic accounts of the event substantiate the Iraqi perception of a foundation national historical event.

Abu Tabikh's memoirs recount that his new position obliged him personally and financially to the revolution cause, as an Iraqi patriot and a pious Shia respectful of clerical authority. But he was suspicious regarding "left-overs Ottomans mercenary officers", whom, he felt, were insincere in their declaration and were seeking profitable positions in the new Iraqi government. These officers later came back, along with the new regime of King Faysal and behaved in such a way that they turned the Iraqi population against the monarchy and marginalised the true historical leaders of the 1920 revolution.

Abu Tabikh defines the 1920 revolution as an important milestone for the founding of Iraq as a nation. But it was also a failed revolution attempt from notables who bit the British benevolent hand and busted their chances to lead an inevitable home rule government. Eventually, they paved the way of the rise to power of former ex-officers of the Ottoman era with self-interest ambitions, when the British finally decided to instal the Hashemite monarchy. Yet, there is no satisfying explanation to the subsequent voluntary choice by those same notables of a foreign king candidate as though no suitable local national Iraqi statesman could ever be found among themselves.

3. Summary of Amal Vinogradov's article

There are three main interpretations to the causes of the 1920 rising. The contemporary British analysis (Arnold Wilson) insists on the role of anarchical and whimsical tribes being manoeuvred by Hashemite agents from Syria. This interpretation takes for granted that tribes were marginalised, unorganised, incapable of coordinated political actions with urban populations and elites. In reality, tribes were a majority constituent of the Iraqi society, with strong political and economic bonds with their neighbouring cities.

A second modern analysis (Fariq al-Fir'aun) insists on the self-emanated revolutionary movement created by regional tribes, upset with taxes and British rule, which revolted under the guidance of religious and tribal leaders. This analysis minimises the role of the urban elites and political parties in leading the revolt and expressing nationwide objectives and ambitions.

A third modern analysis (Elie Kedouri) pictures a Shia dominated revolution motivated by a struggle for power against the other Sunni Ottoman-Arab part of the Iraqi population with the purpose of creating a separate theocratic Shia entity in the southern part of Iraq.

The author Vinogradov thinks the 1920 revolt was a dramatic response given by rural Iraqi tribes to existential threats put to their way of life and political influence by British rule. Other incentives for action came from contemporary events in Syria, Hijaz and Egypt, showing the way to nationalist consciousness.

The last period of Ottoman rule introduced many changes in education, free press and political awareness and speech. Iraqi political parties and newspapers were created as a reaction to Turkish narrow-minded chauvinism of the Young Turks' CUP. Land tenure system reforms were introduced which resulted in the formal registration (i.e. nationalisation) of "miri" former common-owned tribal 'dira' lands. These lands were then attributed or sold to rich tribal sheikhs and absentee urban landlords with deep consequences in the social structures of Iraq. Ottoman rule was strongest in the three Vilayet capitals of Mosul, Baghdad and Basra, but the countryside was left to the mediation of politically organised tribal confederations. The 2m Iraqi population comprised 8% tribal nomads, 48% tribal semi-nomadic cultivators, 32% villagers and 12% city dwellers. South of Baghdad, most tribes were Shia although with occasional leadership from a Sunni tribe, which undermines a simplistic Sunni-Shia political line of divide. Iraqi society was a complex multi-layered patchwork, with various interactions, bonds, suspicions and a limited sense of national unity, albeit a shared belief in Islam and Arabness. Tribal sheikh leadership was agnatic, based on the prestige of ancestry and problem-solving and warfare capabilities. Ottomans would delegate law and order issues to powerful and subsidised client sheikh. The legal grant of former collective tribal lands to private individual landlords was a powerful tool in the hands of the Ottomans to divide and rule Iraqi society. It opposed a newly formed quasi feudal class to landless nomads and farmers.

Simultaneously, modernity erupted in Iraq : railways, banks, steamships, oil exploration, cash-crop and wool demand etc.). Circumstantial changes in the Euphrates River beds and water volume flows provoked mass migrations and tensions in southern Iraq and the subsequent construction of a dam. The 1920 revolt under British rule came after several decades of enduring and profound changes which had affected tribal social structures and economy. It came amid nationalist political crisis in neighbouring Arab countries such as Syria, heralded by local Iraqi writers and poets. A variety of political parties and secret societies were formed by city notables, tribal leaders and army officers, favouring Arab unity and independence. The Ottoman caliphate was challenged by both Sunni and Shia clerics who favoured an Arab-Moslem-led emirate or kingdom.

The Shia mujtahidin top clerics and the Madrasa al-Ja'fariya in Baghdad for higher education of the Shia youth were key actors in the support of these political objectives in the south and middle Euphrates.

When the British first landed in Basra in November 1914, they proclaimed they came as liberators of the Iraqi population and were at war against the Ottomans only. But both Sunni and Shia Ulemas denounced this foreign invasion by Infidels and mobilised the tribes, which got a first experience of modern warfare against the British. The retreat of the Ottomans settled the war. They abandoned embittered Arab allies who resented the scornful attitude and critics of their vanquished Turkish former masters against them. This situation drove the Iraqis to reconsider their Islamic loyalty and made turn to their own arabness and nationalism.

Unfortunately, British rule lacked consistency and vision for the future of Iraq. Attitude and behaviour of Political Officers varied greatly from one region or one tribe to the other. A lucrative tax levied by the British on Shia burials in the sacred city of Najaf was particularly resented. As early as 1918, southern-Iraq-based secret societies and party Haras al-Istiqlal started organising targeted assassinations and demanding immediate independence. London organised a rigged consultation of Iraqi notables on the future of Iraq, the role of the UK and the name of the Arab ruler. Answers were confused and contradictory but underlined the independence issue. Regional uprising, led by pro-Hashemite officers, in Kurdish areas and in Deir ez-Zor, together with violent British retaliations fuelled general civil unrest, blurring traditional dissent between Shia and Sunni. Mass common religious ceremonies ended in political demonstration rallies which reached momentum during Ramadan in spring 1919. News from the San Remo conference reached Baghdad in June and triggered a formal demand to the British authorities for independence. The newly appointed Shia grand Mujtahed Al-Shirazi liaised between all malcontent parties and promulgated a fatwa confirming the Moslem principle of Iraqi independence against the British infidels.

Armed revolt sparked in Rumaytha with the failed imprisonment of a nationalist Sheikh on tax debt charges. His kinsmen freed him and started destroying railway infrastructures. Soon, an organised armed rebellion spread and a first British garrison was subdued with the help of Iraqi former ottoman officers. In Najaf, a structured provisory government replaced the British governor. Elsewhere, the British were outnumbered and could not keep control over simultaneous insurrections in multiple locations. To prevent a snowball effect, reinforcements including airplanes were sent from Iran. Air strikes lifted the siege laid on Kufa and proved a turning point in the outcome of the rebellion by helping the British forces in regrouping on a defence line in Hilla south of Baghdad.

Parallel conflicts simultaneously occurred when farming tenants revolted against their absentee landlords and Assyrian refugees were used by the British as suppletive forces against rebelling tribes.

The British counter-offensive took the Iraqi rebels off-foot because of their lack of money and shortages in food and ammunitions. Soon, Karbala then Najaf had to surrender and were put under heavy retaliatory fines. Meanwhile, British authorities had changed attitude and instructed Percy Cox with the help of Gertrude Stein to initiate more conciliatory negotiations regarding independence. By November 1920, the revolt was ended and the tribes militarily subdued. Consequently, the British had also begun blending native administration home-rule with their own in Baghdad. The revolt had cost the British government a two-year equivalent of the total budget for administrative and military control of Iraq and thrice the total amount of subsidies given to the WWI Hedjaz Arab revolt.

The British prepared the handing over of Iraq to Faysal as a king. This resolved the political issue of his staying in Syria under French mandate. He also proved more receptive to submission to British indirect rule and cautious against ill-advised radical Arab nationalists. Faysal left Mecca for Baghdad on 13th June 1921, a year after the start of the Iraqi revolt. A new Iraqi government was formed around Nuri Al-Said. British ground troops withdrew except for an RAF base in Habaniyya. The independent Iraq history was officially started in 1921, but the 1920 upheaval stayed in everybody's mind.

4. Personal Comments and Critic - Conclusion

Abbas Kadhim gives a very detailed description of troop movements, battles, casualties and circumstantial events based on first hand documentation and contemporaries' memoirs. But he gives little explanations to the root causes of the rebellion and the origins of Iraqi nationalism. He is also short in explaining why attitudes were different between various regions of Iraq and especially why it was centered in the south and did not spread to the north or Kurdistan during that period. The specificities of the Shia-Sunni split between lower and upper Euphrates are not raised either. He doesn't explain why Baghdad remained so submissive in 1920 while the city took the leadership in the 1941 coup and subsequent uprising.

He goes in thorough details regarding the respective pre-eminence of various individual actors in the rebellion. The first hoisting of the Iraqi flag is an interesting point of interest but not of paramount importance, except in terms of hagiography of specific characters such as Abu Tabikh

and fellow revolutionaries, to whom the author pays much reverence. Finally, he doesn't give an overall view of the short term and longer-term consequences of the failed rebellion for the future of Iraq.

He admits that it is hard to reconstruct feelings and meanings in the mind of the various actors during any past events. Yet, the author indulges in giving too much retrospective insight and vision to the provisory government. He tries to convince the reader on faint feelings that the raising of the flag ceremony had nation-wide significance at the time and that the self-proclaimed government in Karbala was some sort of constituent assembly of representatives from all over the country with all eyes in the countryside directed to it, which is not so obvious nor substantiated.

The author is very harsh, following in that matter the memoirs of Abu Tabikh, regarding the "left-overs Ottoman mercenary officers". He considers that they are all self-interested mercenaries unworthy to be considered as true Arab nationalists. Abbas Kadhim conveys the feeling that the purest expression of Iraqi nationalism is to be found in the 1920 revolt, though anarchic, unstructured and unsuccessful as it may have been, and that the later Faysal regime is a fraud and the military elite around him unworthy of consideration.

He concludes on a paradox. The Shia scholars and notables finally favoured the Hashemite Faysal candidacy for the throne in Iraq. Abbas Kadhim questions this choice as being illogical and hints at a possible quest for legitimacy of an "Al ahl Beyt" descended Hashemite king who would reconcile the gap between Shia and Sunni Iraqis.

Amal Vinogradov had access to memoirs written in Arabic in Iraq and Lebanon and likewise to British autobiographies and diplomatic sources. Her article gives reasonable details on the day-to-day events of the battle front although with much less circumstantial details as Abbas Kadhim. But she describes the major changes the Iraqi society was confronted with, way back starting under the Ottoman rule. She depicts how such aspects as land tenure system changes, new economic and trade flows and the introduction of new international perspectives and technologies fragilized the traditional Iraqi tribal organisation and way of life.

In her opinion, the 1920 upheaval is foremost the reaction of fragilized and anxious Iraqi tribal society. Its anarchic rebellion against the British is the reflection of a last chance stand of nomadic and semi-nomadic tribes against a newly centralised and "control-freak" modern government imposing constraints, limiting self-rule and intrusive in terms of tax collection. The 1920 rebellion is a conflict by independent minded tribes adverse to central authority and levies and protesting the confiscation of free transit and pasture on common lands by way of arbitrary decisions taken in the cities.

According to Vinogradov, these structural causes to the rebellion preceded the arrival of the British in Iraq. Obviously, they were reinforced by other variables such as the animosity of the Moslem clerics and population against a Christian occupation force with an ever-extending length of stay. Of course, active pro-Hashemite clandestine political agitators from Syria and various complex political struggles in neighbouring countries were additional strong incentives to the Iraqi revolution in 1920. Neither paper give enough insight regarding the Shia-Sunni divide or the Kurdish and northern Iraq lack of reaction and participation.

As a conclusion, Vinogradov's paper leads us to the conclusion that this revolt was limited in scope to southern tribes, mainly Shia, attached to a dying or threatened way life, living south of Baghdad, with limited capacity of communication and long-range coordination. It contradicts in part Kadhim's scenario of a would-be national pan-Iraqi revolution. Although, this may be true as a modern nation-building mythology reconstruction.